

CHARACTERISTICS OF TRADITIONAL MONUMENTS RECOVERED FROM THE MUDWALL FORTRESS OF DESHAN KALA, KHIVA CITY

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Abstract: This article presents the different types of historical monuments in the Deshon Fortress in Khiva. It also highlights the advantages of Khivan traditional monuments and the styles of ancient Khorezmian houses.

Keywords: Mud wall, Khiva architecture, monument, clay architecture.

Architecture is one of the fields with deep historical roots. Its development periods coincide with those of humanity. In short, architecture has developed alongside humanity. The following information illustrates this idea. Since the beginning of humanity, people have been searching and striving. Finding something new has always been one of their main goals. This is why residential buildings have developed alongside people. Early humans used natural shelters as their homes. Then, they built huts from various natural materials and lived in them. They used animal skins, wood, and stones as building materials. People then began living in these houses, creating the first examples of dwellings made from a combination of soil, stones, and trees.

Khiva is a museum city with architectural monuments and entire ensembles built by master craftsmen. The architectural art of the Khorezm masters is undoubtedly part of world culture. The ancient palaces, early medieval fortresses, and oldest cities in the oasis are world-famous, testifying to the centuries-old expertise of Khorezmian architecture.

Fig. 1 View of tall pillared porches

The basic plan of traditional Khorezm houses makes extensive use of high verandas (Figure 1), provides for ventilation and heat removal. Also, Khiva

houses do not have earthquake-resistant walls built in two rows within a wooden frame with a thickness of up to 60-70 cm, as in Fergana houses, as well as internal voids and niches. In conditions of low seismic hazard, Khorezm could build single-row wooden frame houses (nigiriki) with walls only 15-20 cm thick. Tokchas were built only in palaces, of course, the number of these rooms was in line with the size of the courtyards and the type of decoration, that is, the richness of their decoration, distinguished them from ordinary residential buildings.

There was a need for residential buildings in the regions of Khiva, Khazorasp, Khanka, and Urgench to be restored in accordance with the surrounding climatic conditions, that is, to merge with nature. This functional feature is reflected in the artistic appearance of summer houses, terraces, and pools. Sun-protection devices that shield the house from heat also contribute to the holistic appearance of the Khorezm residential building's unique functional, private, and artistic composition, as well as its landscaping.

Figure 2. Plan of traditional monuments in the Zargarlar mahalla in Khiva, 19th century

1-entrance; 2-hallway; 3-back porch; 4-large porch; 5-garage; 6-ayvan; 7-side house; 8-kitchen; 9-study

The spatial idea of Khiva houses, developing from the simplest combination of ulli (huge) ter - iwans, goes through several stages: on the one hand, expanding the courtyard area and enriching it with various options for columns, on the other hand, developing towards a closed courtyard. The construction of

the mahalla area and residential areas, combining the typology of residential buildings and public buildings, has created a compositionally diverse silhouette. Full use of colors and textures, connection with the terrain, proper orientation in landscaping and water supply. Functionality arose here, taking into account climatic conditions (Fig. 2). Fig. 2 shows the initial state of a traditional Khiva residential building, divided into all the rooms necessary for living. The finest examples of Khorezmian architecture have been preserved in Khiva. Most of these houses have small courtyards, which were unnecessary. On the contrary, most of the courtyard was covered with a veranda to reduce sunlight.

Figure 3. Traditional monuments in the city of Khiva

The use of the veranda in residential architecture is based on the climatic conditions of the area where the building is located and the location of the rooms. For example, in Khiva, it is designed to freshen the air of the porch, room and yard due to the different climatic conditions, relatively hot weather in summer.

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